

EFFECT OF PHENTHOATE ON PROTEIN LEVELS OF FRESHWATER FISH *LABEO ROHITA* (HAMILTON)

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ABSTRACT

The organophosphorus pesticide Phenthoate has been widely used in agriculture for several crops such as paddy, cotton and vegetables to control serious insects and mites in many areas of India. These chemicals cause severe damage to aquatic ecosystem especially to fishes. The main aim and objective of present study is to evaluate the impact on proteins metabolism in fingerlings of *Labeo rohita* an economically important Indian major carp. The lethal concentration was found to be 2.1mg/l under laboratory condition and 1/10th of lethal concentration for 96hrs LC₅₀ value is considered as sub lethal concentration. The exposure of fish to sub lethal concentration for 1, 4 and 8 days and investigated significant changes in the vital organs by following standard protocols. The results shows that the percentage of proteins degradation was minimum (7.62%) in gut and maximum percentage (11.76%) in liver for 1day, minimum reduction was (8.04 %) in brain and maximum was (13.64%) in liver for 4 days, minimum percentage depletion (8.36 %) in gill and maximum was (22.46%) in liver for 8 days compared to control. The total protein content levels rapidly induced might be due to the pesticide pollution and inhibition of metabolizing enzymes by toxicity. It is concluded that Phenthoate concentrations (low and high) is very toxic and causes alterations in vital organs of fish *L. rohita*.

Key words : Toxicity, protein levels, sub lethal concentration

INTRODUCTION

Water pollution is usually caused by various human sources, typically (point and nonpoint) industrial facilities and agrochemicals especially in aquatic ecosystem, has become a serious environmental problem now a days. These agrochemicals and industrial discharges may carried away effectively by rains, winds, rivers and floods into the large water bodies and change their physico-chemical properties with high toxicity. The water contamination cause damages to aquatic life especially to fishes which are very sensitive to wide range of toxicant in the water (Herger et al., 1995).

Different species of fish show active uptake and accumulation of many toxicants such as herbicides, pesticides, heavy metals and polychlorinated biphenyls from water bodies. Among all these agrochemicals, pesticides found to be extremely toxic to organisms and also to the food chain of aquatic ecosystems. The accumulation of pesticides produces some physiological, biochemical and as well as morphological responses in the freshwater fauna by influencing several activities of metabolites and enzymes reported by Ramamurthy et al. (1987).

The alterations of biochemical contents in different tissues of fish due to toxic impact of different agrochemicals and heavy metals have been reported by number of researchers (Nagrathamma and Ramamurthy, 1982; Desai et al., 2002; Remia et al., 2008; Hadi et al., 2009; Ganeshwade, 2011). Organophosphates are most preferred insecticides in agriculture due to their effectiveness, less persistent life and easy detoxification in animal tissues which directly inhibit AchE (acetylcholinesterase) activity observed by (Rao et al., 2005) in fish and other aquatic organisms.

Phenthoate (alpha-ethoxycarbonylbenzyl O, O - diethyl phosphorodithioate) is commonly known as Phendol 50% EC (Emulsifiable Concentrate) and it is a broad spectrum, noncumulative, organophosphorus pesticide. It is widely used to protect vegetable crops and as well as controls the parasite on animals. *L. rohita* is one of the prime cultured freshwater fish in poly-culture and has tremendous economical importance. The main objective of present study was to assess the impacts of Phenthoate pesticide on the total protein content in the tissues of *Labeo rohita* exposed to sublethal concentration for 1, 4 and 8 days. In order to investigate the percent changes caused by pesticide on protein catabolism was also evaluated along with standard deviation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental design:

Healthy juvenile fresh water fish *L. rohita* measuring with 7.5 ± 1.5 cm in length and 8.5 ± 0.5 gm in body weight were collected from local fish farm at Buddam village in Bapatla mandal, Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh, India. The fishes were acclimatized to laboratory condition for two weeks in large plastic tubs using dechlorinated tap water (Tarsons Pvt. Ltd.), previously washed with 0.1% KMnO₄ solution to free walls from microbial infection. Physico-chemical parameters of water were analyzed by following standard protocol suggested by American Public Health Association (APHA, 2005) having temperature of $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, pH 6.8 \pm 0.05, Dissolved Oxygen 6.9-7.4 mg/L, salinity 0 ppt, and total hardness 170 mg/L as CaCO₃.

During acclimatization, fishes were fed with fish pellets and rice bran on every day after renewing the water.

Preparation of Stock Solution:

Stock solution of Phenthoate was prepared by dissolving 1 gram of pesticide in 100 ml of acetone (stock solution) and the required quantity of Phenthoate was drawn from the stock solution to maintain the suitable concentration of 1 mg/L in the container. The fish were separated into several groups and each containing 10 individuals and pilot experiments were conducted to drive the LC₅₀ determinations. These groups were exposed to different concentrations, for acute toxicity estimation, ranged from 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6, 2.0, 2.4, 2.8, 3.2, 3.6 and 4.0 mg/L for 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours. During the whole experiment a control group was maintained with acetone for comparison.

The fish were not fed on the day before the beginning of the experiment. The concentration of the pesticide caused 50% mortality at 96 h exposure was taken as the LC₅₀ value in the test organisms. Each day number of dead fish were counted and removed immediately from the test container. Percent mortality was carried out and the values were pooled up into probit scale. These values were determined and analyzed by using Finney's Probit analysis (Finney, 1971). The LC₅₀ values obtained by the method given by the committee of aquatic toxicity (Anon, 1975). The 96 h LC₅₀ value of Phenthoate to fish *L. rohita* was found to be 2.1 mg/L. Then the fish were exposed to sublethal concentrations of 1/10th 96 h of LC₅₀ value i.e., 0.21 mg/L for 1, 4 and 8 days respectively. A suitable control was also maintained to nullify any other effects that likely to affect the fish. Then the fishes were scarified immediately and isolated fresh (wet) tissue of vital organs such as brain, gill, liver, kidney, gut and muscle for estimation of the total proteins.

Estimation of total proteins:

The total protein content of the pesticide exposed tissue samples were estimated according to the modified standard method (Lowry et al., 1951). The Quantity of 5% homogenate of brain, gill, kidney, liver, muscle

and gut were isolated, precipitated with 5% TCA then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The precipitate was dissolved in 1 ml of 1N NaOH solution and 0.2 ml of extract taken into test tube and mixed with 5 ml of alkaline copper solution. To this 0.5 ml of 50% Folin Phenol reagent was added after 30 minutes, the optical density was measured at 540 nm against the blank. The standard graph was plotted by using Lowry's method with bovine serum albumin (BSA) as standard solution. The values are expressed as mg/g wet weight of the tissue.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean values obtained for total proteins in different tissues of fish and percent change over control along with standard deviation are given in Table 1 and 2 and are graphically represented in Figure 1 and 2. In one day control fish of *L. rohita*, the total protein content is in the order of liver > muscle > kidney > brain > gill > gut. During the exposure of lethal concentration of Phenthoate, percent change of total protein depletes in the order of liver > muscle > brain > kidney > gill > gut. During one day sublethal exposure maximum %change was observed in liver (11.76%) and minimum %change was shown in brain (5.03%) when compared with the control (Figure 1).

Table-1: Changes in the total protein (mg/g wet weight of tissue) content in different tissues of *Labeo rohita* on exposure to Phenthoate for 24 hours

Organs	Control (1 Day)	Lethal	% change (Control Vs. Lethal)	Sublethal (1 Day)	% change (Control Vs. Sublethal)
Brain	113.78± 0.005	95.02± 0.01	16.48 %	108.06± 0.005	5.03 %
Gill	110.02± 0.03	94.03± 0.005	14.53 %	102.99± 0.007	6.38 %
Kidney	116.6± 0.005	98.06± 0.004	15.90 %	106.20± 0.005	8.92 %
Liver	149.57± 0.01	110.04± 0.005	26.42 %	132.03± 0.05	11.76 %
Muscle	132.20± 0.003	109.02± 0.03	17.53 %	121.03±0.005	8.45 %
Gut	108.4±0.01	93.14± 0.003	10.38 %	100.15±0.005	7.62 %

Data are mean of five values ± SD.

Table-2: Changes in the total protein (mg/g wet weight of tissue) in different tissues of *Labeo rohita* on exposure to Phenthoate for 4 days and for 8 days

Organs	Control (4 days)	Sublethal (4 days)	% change (Control Vs. Sublethal)	Control (8 days)	Sublethal (8 days)	% change (Control Vs. Sublethal)
Brain	109.00 ± 0.006	100.24 ± 0.005	8.04 %	101.62 ± 0.005	92.81 ± 0.005	8.66%
Gill	106.24 ± 0.03	97.16 ± 0.007	8.55 %	97.26 ± 0.02	89.13 ± 0.03	8.36%
Kidney	109.35 ± 0.05	99.20 ± 0.005	9.28 %	95.34 ± 0.01	83.53 ± 0.02	12.39%
Liver	138.05 ± 0.01	119.22 ± 0.04	13.64 %	117.43 ± 0.02	91.05 ± 0.04	22.46%
Muscle	127.43 ± 0.004	112.15 ± 0.015	11.99 %	118.45 ± 0.005	97.23 ± 0.03	17.91%
Gut	104.11 ± 0.03	93.14 ± 0.05	10.54 %	93.22 ± 0.006	85.61 ± 0.006	8.16%

Data are mean of five values ± SD.

exposure of pesticide mixture Monocrotophos and Fenvalerate. Suneetha (2011) and Tantarapale (2011) reported the changes in carbohydrate metabolism with the mixture of Endosulfan and Fenvalerate on *L. rohita*.

The decreased trend of protein content in various tissues of *L. rohita* in the present study may be due to metabolic utilization of keto acids in the synthesis of glucose or for the osmotic and ionic regulation as mention by Schmidt (1975), Vutukuru (2005), Venktrama et al., (2006), Muley (2007), Mamata Kumari (2007), Chezhan et al., (2010) and Murthy and Devi (1982). The present study revealed the reduction in protein levels in the tissues of *L. rohita* by following acute exposure of toxicant Phenthoate. Similar change was observed in *C. punctatus* exposed to technical grade malathion by Agrhari et al. (2006) and Tilak et al., (2003) explained the reduction of protein content of liver, brain and ovary of *C. punctatus* exposed to fenvalerate.

CONCLUSION

The present work indicates that Phenthoate causes alterations in the protein metabolism of fresh water fish *L. rohita*. Thus alteration in protein content in different tissues of the fish during the exposure to the chemical Phenthoate naturally affects the nutritive value of fish.

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